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PUBLIC CONTROL IN THE ADMINISTRATION OF GOVERNMENT AND PUBLIC AFFAIRS

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Annotation: Another important legal basis for public control and its implementation in the management of society and state affairs is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Environmental Control". It is noteworthy that this article states that public control can be carried out in cooperation with the mass media, non-governmental non-profit organizations and other organizations, that state bodies must assist citizens' self-government bodies in the implementation of public control and take timely measures in accordance with legal documents regarding their appeals. related norms were also strengthened.

Key words: society, state, public control, interest of citizens.

In our country, civil society institutions and non-governmental organizations are becoming an important factor in protecting democratic values, human rights and freedoms, and legal interests. The importance of these institutions is incomparable in realizing the potential of citizens, in creating conditions for increasing their social, socio-economic activity and legal culture, in helping to ensure the balance of interests in society, and in introducing effective and practical mechanisms of public control in state and community management.

The Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, developed at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, plays an important role in increasing the efficiency of the performance of tasks assigned to state bodies, and establishing public control over their observance of human rights, freedoms and interests.

As the head of our state, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, rightly criticized in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, "... to date, clear legal mechanisms for effective public control over the activities of state bodies have not been created. This prevents non-governmental non-profit organizations from objectively evaluating the activities of state bodies and officials. Based on this, it is necessary to adopt the Law "On Public Control" in order to introduce effective and practical mechanisms of public control in the administration of the state and society. In this regard, I propose to establish public councils that will operate under all state bodies. These public councils should fulfill the function of a

bridge that ensures the openness of the activities of state bodies and connects them directly with the population.¹

A number of measures have been taken to improve the legal foundations of civil society institutions in our country. In particular, the new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" was adopted and published in the press on April 23, 2013, and entered into force from this date.² In this law, public control is to study the state of implementation of laws and other legal documents in the relevant territory by self-governing bodies of citizens; apply to state authorities for taking appropriate measures; it was stated that it is possible to send requests on matters of social importance within the competence of state bodies and in other forms in accordance with legal documents (Article 16).

Another important legal basis for public control and its implementation in the management of society and state affairs is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Environmental Control".

It is noteworthy that this article states that public control can be carried out in cooperation with the mass media, non-governmental non-profit organizations and other organizations, that state bodies must assist citizens' self-government bodies in the implementation of public control and take timely measures in accordance with legal documents regarding their appeals. related norms were also strengthened. This, in turn, is evidence that today civil society institutions, including citizens' self-government bodies, are becoming one of the important means of ensuring effective interaction of citizens with the state, determining people's mood, and their reaction to the changes taking place in the country.

In the Law "On Environmental Control" adopted by the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 12, 2013, approved by the Senate on December 12, 2013 and announced in the press on December 28, 2013, citizens are designated as subjects of environmental control (Article 8). , rights and obligations in the system of ensuring environmental protection and rational use of

¹ Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis // Xalk sozi, issue of December 22, 2017.

² The new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2013, No. 17, Article 219

natural resources were strengthened (Article 17).³ According to Article 9 of this Law, public environmental control was defined as a special type of environmental control. In addition, the institutions of civil society were empowered to form a system of public inspectors of environmental control and coordinate their activities. Public inspectors have the authority to monitor the compliance of legal entities and individuals with the legal document in the field of environmental protection and rational use of natural resources, to participate in public environmental expertise and other powers (Article 18).

Such institute of public inspectors is now widely used in the practice of nature protection in countries such as USA, Great Britain, Germany, and Korea.

It is worth noting that special attention is being paid to the formation of the constitutional basis for the implementation of public control over the implementation of legal documents by the state authorities and management bodies in our country and the development of mechanisms for the implementation of public control over the activities of state bodies. In fact, "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan" approved by the XIV plenary session of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 10, 2014 and signed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, announced in the press on April 17, 2014. The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Articles (32, 78, 93, 98, 103 and 117) is aimed at further strengthening the role of citizens in the implementation of public control over the activities of state power, and the consistent implementation of the constitutional principle of separation of powers.

In particular, Article 32 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan included a norm that provides for the participation of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the management of society and state affairs through the development and improvement of public control over the activities of state bodies. society and state affairs. Also, the second part of Article 32 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was supplemented with the norm "The procedure for public control over the activities of state bodies shall be determined by law." The inclusion of this norm in

³ The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Articles 32, 78, 93, 98, 103 and 117)" // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2014, No. 16, Article 177.

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our Basic Law will serve to develop the legal basis for the implementation of public control over the activities of state bodies in our country.

In fact, the analysis of the laws adopted during the years of independence shows that although some of them have norms about public control, there are no special rules that provide for the types of control, the methods and forms of its implementation, and control mechanisms in general. In turn, the norm included in the second part of Article 32 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is how important it is to adopt the law "On Public Control in the Republic of Uzbekistan", which strengthens the concept of public control in our country, its types and forms, the principles of its implementation and the legal mechanisms of their implementation. In paragraph 33 of the State Program on the implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of supporting active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and technologies", it is recommended to introduce effective and practical mechanisms of public control in the management of the state and society. the task of adopting the draft law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Control" was established⁴

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⁴ The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Program for the implementation of the action strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of supporting active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and technologies" // National database of legal documents, 23.01. 2018, No. 06/18/5308/0610; 05/25/2018, No. 06/18/5447/1269

